

Supporting Information

Figure S1: Exemplary predictive posterior mean probability maps of the habitat suitability derived from SDMs in the terrestrial (A, *Eucalyptus punctata*), marine (B, *Epinephelus morio*) and freshwater realms (C, *Chondrostoma nasus*), each using a specific planning unit shape (grids, hexagons, sub-catchments). Right and left hand columns represent the predictions from non-spatial and spatial models, respectively, along with the AUC and TSS scores. We transformed the predictive posterior mean probability maps into a semi-binary scheme using TSS as a threshold (?), where all values below the threshold were converted to zero and values above the threshold retained their original values. All predictions can be accessed via the online Supporting Information at <https://doi.pangaea.de/10.1594/PANGAEA.889033>.

Figure S2: Differences in summed habitat suitability predictions derived from non-spatial and spatial SDMs in the terrestrial (A), marine (B) and freshwater realm (C), each using a specific shape of the planning unit. Blue and red areas represent planning units where non-spatial and spatial SDMs predicted a higher habitat suitability across all species, respectively.

Figure S3: (A-I) Spatial arrangement of potential protected areas derived from non-spatial and spatial SDMs, as well as their overlap in the **terrestrial** realm for conservation targets ranging from 10-50%, using a 10% gap to optimality.

Figure S4: (A-I) Spatial arrangement of potential protected areas derived from non-spatial and spatial SDMs, as well as their overlap in the **marine** realm for conservation targets ranging from 10-50%, using a 10% gap to optimality.

Figure S5: (A-I) Spatial arrangement of potential protected areas derived from non-spatial and spatial SDMs, as well as their overlap in the **freshwater** realm for conservation targets ranging from 10-50%, using a 10% gap to optimality.

Figure S6: Calibration of the boundary length modifier (BLM) for the spatial prioritisation in the terrestrial (A), marine (B) and freshwater (C) realms.

Table S1: All environmental predictors used in the terrestrial, marine and freshwater species distribution models, the aggregation method within the planning units, the original spatial grain, and the source where the data was obtained. Abbreviations: avg, average; sd, standard deviation.

Realm	Predictor	Aggregation	Unit	Spatial grain	Source
Terrestrial	Mean diurnal temperature range	avg	°C	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Temperature seasonality	avg	-	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Temperature seasonality	sd	-	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Max. temperature of warmest period	avg	°C	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Annual precipitation	avg	mm	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Annual precipitation	sd	mm	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Precipitation of driest period	avg	mm	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Mean moisture index of highest quarter	avg	index	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Mean moisture index of highest quarter	sd	index	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Mutliresolution valleybottom flatness	avg	index	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Ruggedness	avg	-	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Median topographic wetness	sd	-	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Maximum topographic wetness	sd	-	250 m	?
Terrestrial	Cultivated and managed vegetation	avg	%	1 km	earthenv.org/landcover
Terrestrial	Urban/built-up area	avg	%	1 km	earthenv.org/landcover
Terrestrial	Barren land cover	avg	%	1 km	earthenv.org/landcover
Marine	Temperature	avg	°C	9 km	bio-oracle.org
Marine	Current velocity	avg	m ⁻¹	9 km	bio-oracle.org
Marine	Photosynthetically Active Radiation	avg	E m ⁻² day ⁻¹	9 km	bio-oracle.org
Marine	Light at bottom	avg	-	9 km	bio-oracle.org
Marine	Salinity	avg	PSS	9 km	bio-oracle.org
Marine	Silicate	avg	mol m ⁻³	9 km	bio-oracle.org
Marine	Plan Curvature	avg	-	1 km	marspec.org
Marine	Profile Curvature	avg	-	1 km	marspec.org
Marine	Distance to Shore	avg	km	1 km	marspec.org
Marine	Bathymetric Slope	avg	°	1 km	marspec.org
Marine	Depth of the seafloor	avg	m	1 km	marspec.org
Freshwater	Mean annual temperature	avg	°C	1 km	worldclim.org
Freshwater	Temperature annual range	avg	°C	1 km	worldclim.org
Freshwater	Annual precipitation	sum	mm	1 km	worldclim.org
Freshwater	Precipitation seasonality	avg	mm	1 km	worldclim.org
Freshwater	Slope	avg	°	1 km	earthenv.org/topography
Freshwater	Forest cover	avg	%	1 km	earthenv.org/landcover
Freshwater	Urban built up areas	avg	%	1 km	earthenv.org/landcover
Freshwater	Number of dams	sum	count	point data	gwsp.org/products/grand-database

Table S2: Spatial autocorrelation in species occurrence data. Moran I statistics and associated p -values for each taxa within the terrestrial (33), marine (53) and freshwater (85) realm.

Taxon	Realm	Moran's I	p-value
Eucalyptus punctata	terrestrial	0.508770415	0.001
Eucalyptus sieberi	terrestrial	0.480868526	0.001
Eucalyptus pilularis	terrestrial	0.468759566	0.001
Eucalyptus piperita	terrestrial	0.544113802	0.001
Eucalyptus pauciflora	terrestrial	0.353878909	0.001
Eucalyptus agglomerata	terrestrial	0.340538788	0.001
Corymbia maculata	terrestrial	0.438987292	0.001
Eucalyptus dives	terrestrial	0.266819269	0.001
Eucalyptus cypellocarpa	terrestrial	0.468544948	0.001
Eucalyptus moluccana	terrestrial	0.263419757	0.001
Eucalyptus obliqua	terrestrial	0.370575639	0.001
Eucalyptus fastigata	terrestrial	0.352448679	0.001
Eucalyptus rossii	terrestrial	0.299549201	0.001
Eucalyptus robusta	terrestrial	0.386954707	0.001
Eucalyptus deanei	terrestrial	0.424191001	0.001
Corymbia eximia	terrestrial	0.441368802	0.001
Angophora bakeri	terrestrial	0.44009549	0.001
Eucalyptus dalrympleana (southern subsp.)	terrestrial	0.203971009	0.001
Eucalyptus blaxlandii	terrestrial	0.363489149	0.001
Eucalyptus quadrangulata	terrestrial	0.231146533	0.001
Eucalyptus delegatensis (subsp. delegatensis)	terrestrial	0.260801564	0.001
Eucalyptus ovata	terrestrial	0.187335033	0.001
Eucalyptus oreades	terrestrial	0.220704824	0.001
Eucalyptus fraxinoides	terrestrial	0.206716163	0.001
Eucalyptus dalrympleana (northern subsp.)	terrestrial	0.17918254	0.001
Eucalyptus tricarpa	terrestrial	0.437386746	0.001
Eucalyptus squamosa	terrestrial	0.239911096	0.001
Eucalyptus cinerea	terrestrial	0.178287103	0.001
Eucalyptus niphophila	terrestrial	0.172866737	0.001
Eucalyptus aggregata	terrestrial	0.076687554	0.001
Eucalyptus luehmanniana	terrestrial	0.366410819	0.001
Eucalyptus obstans	terrestrial	0.258280444	0.001
Eucalyptus stenostoma	terrestrial	0.165376511	0.001
Centropristis striata	marine	0.236193597	0.001
Balistes capriscus	marine	0.224701945	0.001
Haemulon aurolineatum	marine	0.236587968	0.001

Taxon	Realm	Moran's I	p-value
Centropristis ocyurus	marine	0.209551518	0.001
Pagrus pagrus	marine	0.244123351	0.001
Rhomboplites aurorubens	marine	0.191010055	0.001
Lutjanus campechanus	marine	0.165591656	0.001
Diplectrum formosum	marine	0.165448569	0.001
Mycteroperca phenax	marine	0.244002111	0.001
Epinephelus morio	marine	0.187963644	0.001
Haemulon plumieri	marine	0.218828092	0.001
Mycteroperca microlepis	marine	0.155416262	0.001
Stephanolepis hispida	marine	0.189717725	0.001
Diplodus holbrookii	marine	0.216049086	0.001
Calamus nodosus	marine	0.249381329	0.001
Muraena retifera	marine	0.147106091	0.001
Stenotomus chrysops	marine	0.201462302	0.001
Gymnothorax moringa	marine	0.137073271	0.001
Seriola dumerili	marine	0.169173997	0.001
Lagodon rhomboides	marine	0.177008032	0.001
Epinephelus niveatus	marine	0.177535199	0.001
Chaetodon ocellatus	marine	0.099114032	0.001
Seriola rivoliana	marine	0.164118098	0.001
Calamus leucosteus	marine	0.078333248	0.001
Equetus umbrosus	marine	0.049896791	0.001
Epinephelus drummondhayi	marine	0.209424567	0.001
Holacanthus bermudensis	marine	0.123272164	0.001
Lopholatilus chamaeleonticeps	marine	0.35820508	0.001
Gymnothorax vicinus	marine	0.099877406	0.001
Echeneis naucrates	marine	0.055002313	0.001
Equetus lanceolatus	marine	0.075972163	0.001
Chaetodon sedentarius	marine	0.067368324	0.001
Rypticus maculatus	marine	0.082993559	0.001
Orthopristis chrysoptera	marine	0.10076946	0.001
Caulolatilus microps	marine	0.094034364	0.001
Gymnothorax saxicola	marine	0.128772948	0.001
Opsanus pardus	marine	0.044639899	0.002
Holocentrus ascensionis	marine	0.051128678	0.001
Carcharhinus signatus	marine	0.176094843	0.001
Sphoeroides maculatus	marine	0.185523352	0.001
Epinephelus adscensionis	marine	0.131133005	0.001

Taxon	Realm	Moran's I	p-value
Urophycis floridana	marine	0.08287226	0.001
Ophichthus ocellatus	marine	0.182404541	0.001
Cephalopholis fulva	marine	0.091728519	0.001
Epinephelus nigritus	marine	0.139692088	0.001
Helicolenus dactylopterus	marine	0.294219901	0.001
Bodianus pulchellus	marine	0.110127672	0.001
Cephalopholis cruentata	marine	0.08387624	0.001
Seriola fasciata	marine	0.059803816	0.001
Caranx crysos	marine	0.073441382	0.001
Seriola zonata	marine	0.031748934	0.013
Lutjanus synagris	marine	0.034917723	0.008
Squalus acanthias	marine	0.095549562	0.001
Salmo trutta fario	freshwater	0.41902073	0.001
Squalius cephalus	freshwater	0.249703306	0.001
Oncorhynchus mykiss	freshwater	0.370107599	0.001
Thymallus thymallus	freshwater	0.330498042	0.001
Cottus gobio	freshwater	0.377961039	0.001
Barbatula barbatula	freshwater	0.300376501	0.001
Alburnus alburnus	freshwater	0.142679279	0.001
Rutilus rutilus	freshwater	0.146101974	0.001
Barbus barbus	freshwater	0.153694661	0.001
Alburnoides bipunctatus	freshwater	0.224442751	0.001
Gobio gobio	freshwater	0.201674931	0.001
Chondrostoma nasus	freshwater	0.172296194	0.001
Perca fluviatilis	freshwater	0.130418342	0.001
Esox lucius	freshwater	0.145739076	0.001
Carassius gibelio	freshwater	0.141246416	0.001
Phoxinus phoxinus	freshwater	0.370615399	0.001
Gobio obtusirostris	freshwater	0.297036141	0.001
Rhodeus amarus	freshwater	0.153138151	0.001
Leuciscus leuciscus	freshwater	0.120736707	0.001
Barbus balcanicus	freshwater	0.33581657	0.001
Cobitis elongatoides	freshwater	0.239069375	0.001
Abramis brama	freshwater	0.113882336	0.001
Pseudorasbora parva	freshwater	0.09477765	0.001
Scardinius erythrophthalmus	freshwater	0.126511114	0.001
Hucho hucho	freshwater	0.191207916	0.001
Cyprinus carpio	freshwater	0.150065707	0.001

Taxon	Realm	Moran's I	p-value
Sabanejewia balcanica	freshwater	0.24121746	0.001
Lepomis gibbosus	freshwater	0.110819687	0.001
Tinca tinca	freshwater	0.165381765	0.001
Lota lota	freshwater	0.070729058	0.001
Barbus petenyi	freshwater	0.450716344	0.001
Phoxinus marsilii	freshwater	0.253262118	0.001
Sander lucioperca	freshwater	0.08442643	0.001
Salmo trutta (brook)	freshwater	0.282261724	0.001
Silurus glanis	freshwater	0.092066607	0.001
Aspius aspius	freshwater	0.094939836	0.001
Blicca bjoerkna	freshwater	0.090549185	0.001
Telestes souffia	freshwater	0.175857468	0.001
Cottus metae	freshwater	0.42368606	0.001
Rutilus virgo	freshwater	0.192775324	0.001
Leuciscus idus	freshwater	0.081836551	0.001
Vimba vimba	freshwater	0.091681065	0.001
Salvelinus fontinalis	freshwater	0.104373351	0.001
Gymnocephalus cernua	freshwater	0.075464125	0.001
Eudontomyzon vladykovi	freshwater	0.265712323	0.001
Carassius carassius	freshwater	0.111692263	0.001
Romanogobio kesslerii	freshwater	0.096771105	0.001
Romanogobio albipinnatus	freshwater	0.048637222	0.001
Misgurnus fossilis	freshwater	0.05368373	0.001
Proterorhinus marmoratus	freshwater	0.050778212	0.001
Zingel zingel	freshwater	0.054897986	0.001
Zingel streber	freshwater	0.04755855	0.001
Cobitis elongata	freshwater	0.146757255	0.001
Anguilla anguilla	freshwater	0.054990749	0.001
Ameiurus nebulosus	freshwater	0.111907457	0.001
Romanogobio vladykovi	freshwater	0.140387546	0.001
Cobitis taenia	freshwater	0.078541685	0.001
Gymnocephalus schraetser	freshwater	0.119905409	0.001
Neogobius fluviatilis	freshwater	0.032836325	0.007
Umbra krameri	freshwater	0.038191194	0.006
Ameiurus melas	freshwater	0.039725377	0.004
Ctenopharyngodon idella	freshwater	0.112944961	0.001
Salmo labrax (brook form)	freshwater	0.347724874	0.001
Eudontomyzon mariae	freshwater	0.200994717	0.001

Taxon	Realm	Moran's I	p-value
Salvelinus umbla	freshwater	0.053241223	0.002
Ballerus ballerus	freshwater	0.058700147	0.001
Ballerus sapa	freshwater	0.008801629	0.063
Cottus poecilopus	freshwater	0.264791148	0.001
Barbus peloponnesius	freshwater	0.107064301	0.001
Gymnocephalus baloni	freshwater	0.03512545	0.012
Leucaspius delineatus	freshwater	0.000150748	0.174
Acipenser ruthenus	freshwater	0.026689203	0.003
Gobio uranoscopus	freshwater	0.076582877	0.001
Carassius auratus	freshwater	0.00933483	0.037
Gasterosteus aculeatus	freshwater	0.052067467	0.004
Ponticola kessleri	freshwater	0.026423969	0.014
Sabanejewia aurata	freshwater	0.022272891	0.014
Romanogobio uranoscopus	freshwater	0.048025099	0.002
Eudontomyzon danfordi	freshwater	0.068484656	0.001
Neogobius melanostomus	freshwater	0.029497087	0.005
Phoxinellus alepidotus	freshwater	0.470973011	0.001
Salmo trutta lacustris	freshwater	-0.000989665	0.43
Hypophthalmichthys molitrix	freshwater	0.02878686	0.007
Perccottus glenii	freshwater	0.031661107	0.005
Pelecus cultratus	freshwater	0.016699162	0.014